

DEVELOPMENT OF DISCOURSE COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation. *The paper addresses the issue of the place of the discourse competence within the framework of a foreign language communicative competence with the aim of foreign language teaching. The author compares and discusses the well-known models of foreign language communicative competence, gives the definition of the term “discourse competence”, as well as compares the meaning of the Uzbek and English terms “discourse competence”.*

Key words: *discourse, discourse competence, communicative competence, goals of teaching a foreign language.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается вопрос о месте дискурсивной компетенции в рамках иноязычной коммуникативной компетенции с целью обучения иностранному языку. Автор сравнивает и рассматривает известные модели иноязычной коммуникативной компетенции, дает определение термину «дискурсивная компетенция», а также сравнивает значение узбекского и английского терминов «дискурсивная компетенция».*

Ключевые слова: *дискурс, дискурсивная компетенция, коммуникативная компетенция, цели обучения иностранному языку.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada chet tilini o‘qitish maqsadida chet tilining kommunikativ kompetensiyasi doirasida nutq kompetensiyasining o‘rni masalasi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Muallif chet tilidagi kommunikativ kompetensiyaning mashhur modellarini qiyoslaydi va muhokama qiladi, “diskurs kompetensiyasi” atamasining ta’rifini beradi, shuningdek, o‘zbek va ingliz tilidagi “diskurs kompetensiyasi” atamalarining ma’nosini solishtiradi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *diskurs, diskurs kompetensiyasi, kommunikativ kompetensiya, chet tilini o‘qitish maqsadlari.*

An important goal of teaching a foreign language to secondary school and university students is the development of foreign language communicative competence. It, in turn, consists of a number of sub competencies [1-4]. Despite the fact that most scientists agreed with the construct of foreign language communicative competence as a whole, they did not come to a common opinion regarding the components of sub competencies and their content. In particular, in one of the first works devoted to the development of models of foreign language communicative competence, M. Canale and M. Swain [5] proposed three components of sub competence: grammatical, sociolinguistic and strategic. Several years later, M. Canale [6] refined this model and identified another, fourth, sub competence - discursive competence. Analysis of the first models allows us to assert that scientists put their conceptual content into some terms denoting sub competences. In particular, “grammatical competence” in its conceptual content corresponded to “linguistic competence”, since it included not only mastery of the grammatical structure of the language being studied, but also mastery of vocabulary and phonology.

Sociolinguistic sub competence included both the variability of speech utterance depending on the social context of communication, which is traditionally the subject of study of sociolinguistics, and the sociocultural component, consisting of knowledge of this very social and cultural context of communication. In this regard, it can be argued that M. Canale and M. Swain significantly limited the conceptual content of sociocultural competence, reducing it exclusively to knowledge of the social context of using a foreign language.

Discursive competence includes two main concepts – “cohesion” and “coherence”. Cohesion is the coherence of words in a sentence and the coherence of sentences among themselves in the text. Coherence is the grammatical, stylistic, logical-semantic integrity of the text.

The model of foreign language communicative competence by M. Canale and M. Swain formed the basis of hundreds of scientific studies by American and European scientists. In Europe, the model of foreign language communicative competence by M. Canale and M. Swain was slightly modified and refined in the study by Van Eck [7], who, taking into account the criticism of the first model, identified six sub competencies: linguistic, sociolinguistic, social, sociocultural, discursive and strategic. Obviously, linguistic competence, which includes a person’s mastery of the grammar, vocabulary and phonology of the foreign language being studied, corresponds in content to the grammatical sub competence of the model by M. Canale and M. Swain. However, in his model, Van Eck divided and separately presented sociolinguistic, sociocultural and social sub competences.

It should be noted that the social sub competence was first identified and presented by the author. By doing so, Van Eck draws the attention of the pedagogical community to the fact that communication and its results depend on both the socio-cultural situation of communication and the social roles that speakers follow in the process of communication. The discursive component is also presented in Van Eck's model. Its content does not differ from the component of the same name in the model of M. Canale and M. Swain.

It should be noted that both Van Eck and M. Canale and M. Swain included a strategic sub competence in their models of foreign language communicative competence. This sub competence is responsible for overcoming language and information gaps by pupils and students that can inevitably appear in the process of foreign language communication.

In addition to the models of M. Canale and M. Swain and Van Eck, the model of communicative abilities developed by Lyle Bachman [8] has become widely known in Western scientific literature. Based on the difference between the term’s “competence” (as a knowledge category) and “performance” (as an activity category), Bachman proposed using the more correct, in his opinion, term “communicative ability”. By doing so, he focused on how the learner can use the acquired knowledge of a foreign language in real oral or written communication. In its structure, the model of communicative abilities differs significantly from all other previously developed models of foreign language communicative competence. The scientist distinguishes two main types of competence - organizational (grammatical and textual components (coherence of speech utterance)) and pragmatic (social and cultural aspect of communication, as well as the functional aspect of communication). In essence, the content of L. Bachman’s model of communicative ability coincides with the content of models of foreign language communicative competence of other authors, but in their structure, these are fundamentally different models.

Educational and cognitive sub competence means the ability of an individual to engage in self-education outside of class time or after graduation throughout life. On the one hand, it may seem strange to include in the model of foreign language communicative competence an aspect that will be universal for any subject of the academic cycle. On the other hand, as P.V. Sysoev [15] asserts, by separately identifying the educational and cognitive sub competence, I.L. Bim wanted to: a) emphasize the importance of developing the skills to engage in self-education in and about a foreign language; b) focus on the fact that a foreign language as an object of study has specific properties that require adapting universal skills directly to teaching a foreign language and the culture of the countries of the native and studied languages.

In the context of our study, the main interest is in the development of discursive competence of third-level (postgraduate) students. In this regard, we will dwell in more detail on such concepts as "discursive competence" and "discourse". In linguistic and pedagogical research, these terms have all sorts of interpretations. Let us consider some of the definitions. M. Canale understands discursive competence as "the ability to combine grammatical forms and meaning to achieve unity in spoken and written text" [6: 9]. The developer of the pan-European model of foreign language communicative competence understands discursive competence as "the ability to use appropriate strategies in communication and for interpreting texts". Text is understood as "any fragment of spoken or written text, of any volume, distinguished by unity" [7: 47].

In the process of teaching foreign languages, there is a mutual influence of speech competence in the native language and speech competence in a foreign language. The development of intercultural speech competence, necessary for using language as a means of communication in a foreign-language multicultural environment, is hardly possible without the parallel formation and development of the corresponding socio-cultural competence" [19: 43]. N.V. Popova understands discursive competence as "the ability to create a coherent speech utterance, while maintaining thematic organization, cohesion, coherence, rhetorical effectiveness and logic within the framework of a real communication situation and an adequate functional style" [20: 75].

An analysis of the above definitions of the terms "discursive competence" and "speech competence" indicates that they are identical in their conceptual content. Discursive, or speech, competence is a person's ability to produce a coherent oral or written statement, characterized by cohesion and coherence, as well as to adequately interpret a foreign-language statement when reading or listening. Discursive, or speech, competence is inextricably linked with all other subcompetencies of foreign-language communicative competence (grammatical and sociocultural/intercultural) and is formed in students along with other components. Some discursive/speech skills (abilities) may be universal and can be transferred from the native language to a foreign language (in the absence of sociocultural conflicts and sociocultural lacunae).

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